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ABSTRACT

This report presents recent new developments of industrial electron accelerators for radiation processing. The engineering solutions for accelerator developments are described. Their technical and parametric features were simulated using the LAE 10/10 and ILU 6 accelerators, to study some aspect of their new possible applications in polymer treatment, seeds disinfestation and paper treatment. The results of the study demonstrated the possibilities in the technology implementation of the specific accelerators being developed. A very important issue is integration of the electron accelerator with the beam system used for material exposure to the electron beam. The conclusions of the report support a broad possibility of new accelerator technology applications, however their acceptance by industry depends on the availability of reliable accelerators at competitive prices.

ARIES Consortium, 2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Z. Zimek, M. Walo, U. Gryczka, D. Chmielewska - Smietanko	INCT	23/10/19
Edited by	R. Edgecock	HUD	24/10/19
Reviewed by	A. G. Chmielewski	INCT	24/10/19
	R. Edgecock	HUD	
	Y. Kadi	CERN	31/10/19
Approved by	M. Vretenar Steering Committee		07/11/19

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Executive summary

The progress in accelerator technology dedicated to industrial applications is closely related to the continuously advanced development in many branches of technology and to technology transition from research to commercially applicable systems. Accelerators may play a major role in developing new, big markets related to radiation processing. However, high power, high efficiency, low cost accelerator technology may need government support in design, construction and testing at demonstration plants. Environmental applications of Electron Beam (EB) technology are examples of high risk and not very high payoff although radiation technology transfer to environmental application could result in substantial improvements in public health.

In the design of accelerators for radiation processing, some selection criteria should be followed to optimize the final economic effect of radiation facility exploitation: high average beam power (productivity), high electron energy (penetration), low price (investment cost), high electrical efficiency (cost of accelerator exploitation), small footprint (building geometry and size), high reliability (availability >95%). A detailed technical analysis should be performed to recognize the optimal conditions of the irradiation process, depending on the geometry of the irradiated product, to define the nominal energy of the accelerator and the configuration of the irradiation process.

The development of compact superconducting accelerators may open many new application areas in energy production such as petroleum upgrading, and liquefying gaseous products. A high power, high energy compact accelerator would be small enough to be installed as a mobile unit. New ideas for accelerators for radiation processing include: superconducting RF compact, high power, electron linacs, eFFAG (Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient compact CW recirculating accelerators), compact CW linacs and number of other modern accelerator constructions. It should be noticed that while many laboratories conduct R&D in accelerator physics, only a few private companies manufacture commercial electron accelerators and they are not ready to provide suitable resources for accelerator technology development. This is an inherent limitation in the sense that new accelerator business can be successful only with new ideas in accelerator design with acceptable costs and performances. However development and implementation of new, high energy efficiency and improved reliability machines is important but not sole requirement regarding its parameters. The integration of the accelerator with material processing line is another important factor, moreover it has to meet requirements of the process: dose delivery rate, depth of electron penetration related to their energy, energy limits related to the origin of the products treated (food, allografts, polymers, electronic devices, gemstones etc). Therefore successful implementation of accelerator based technology is related to the close collaboration between accelerator designers, developers and operators, and chemists, physicians, engineers, economists, etc. Not too many laboratories have such variety of experts to develop electron accelerator technology to the level of Technology Readiness Level 9 (System Test, Launch & Operations). However two of institutions members of ARIES WP3 possess such abilities: namely Fraunhofer FEP of Dresden (Germany) and Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology in Warsaw (Poland). Participation of these institutions in the ARIES project implementation assure direct contact and collaboration between scientist developing a new

accelerator R&D solution and those who are end users of provided equipment. Therefore the second group may provide feedback which should be a basis for a new accelerators parameters development related even to such details like machine size, geometry, beam exit construction etc. The work reported in this Deliverable covered a critical review of recent developments in accelerator engineering and experimental demonstration, and how these machines parameters have to meet requirements of emerging technologies to be implemented with their use. Two types of technologies were selected for such testing; those which require application of low energy beam (less than 300 keV) and highest applicable electron beam energy accepted for eb processing (10 MeV). Two accelerators have been used for testing. The first one was the single cavity, high frequency, pulsed accelerator ILU 6 (with adjustable electron energy up to 2 MeV) and the second the microwave linear electron accelerator, with travelling wave LAE 10/10. The construction principles of both units are different and some of the accelerators being developed and described in the first part of the report are based on similar physics and electronic scientific background. A promising new technology is radiation-induced grafting, a useful tool for surface modification of a wide range of polymers dedicated to different applications. Depending of the product the technology require application of low energy (ca.300 keV) electron beam (battery separators, foils etc) or high energy (10 MeV) beam (bulk materials – like adsorbents and other products treated in suspensions etc). This method, thanks to the choice of suitable monomers, enables the introduction of new properties to the polymer layer such as hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity, adhesion, barrier properties and friction resistance. Radiation grafting has found application in industry and medicine. Currently, intensive work has been carried out in the field of polymer membranes (fuel cell membranes, battery separators), production of selective adsorbents (e.g. scandium, cesium, uranium adsorbents) or to design polymers for medical and biotechnological applications (thermosensitive cell culture surfaces, antibacterial masks, intelligent packagings). Among these applications, membrane systems are one of the most effective and fast-growing technologies used for separation and purification processes. The application of low energy electron beams (up to 300keV) for surface microbial decontamination is being developed as an alternative to currently used highly penetrating ionizing radiation (medical and food products, etc). The low energy electrons can be used for surface microbial decontamination of seeds, flower bulbs or packaging. Elimination of the plant pathogens from the surface of flower bulbs can effectively inhibit the development of the plant disease, reduce spread of the pathogens and prevent the loss of the plants. There are advantages in the application of low energy electron beams, which make it promising technology for many applications. In terms of energy conversion lower energy electron accelerators are more efficient. Thus this technology is more economically profitable and environmentally friendly. Accelerators generating beam of energy below 300 keV are constructed as self-shielded units, which makes them easy to be used in-line of existing processes. The other emerging and very important application of electron accelerator applications is electron beam sanitation of library old books, manuscripts, archives and cultural heritage art crafts. In this case 10 MeV electron energy machines has been applied and both side irradiation is required if bulk items are treated (in some cases surface microbial decontamination maybe applied , but these are random cases). Paper provides the ideal nutrient base for mould fungi. Therefore, large volumes of books

and archival collections are affected by bioburden because of improper storage conditions or accidents such as floods. Protection of books, archives and artefacts from destruction caused by insects and microorganisms is one of the main aims of the cultural heritage objects conservation. Moreover the microbiological burden is harmful for the librarians' and archivists' health as well. Decontamination of microbiologically infected paper-based objects is a new area for the application of electron beam (EB) irradiation.

This report covering information on the recent development of accelerator engineering and presenting the needs regarding requirements their parameters for practical application in different fields of technology is a practical guide for accelerator developers and manufacturers. Experimental demonstration of the importance of these parameters matching with the process requirements gives valuable information for road map elaboration of further developments in accelerator engineering for these solutions, which are being offered to the end users market. This report should be read together with D.3.1. "Application of electron beams in the environmental area" report which presented requirements regarding high power electron accelerators to be applied in environmental pollution technologies. These two reports covers the whole variety of accelerators applied in eb processing and on the basis of full practical and experimental demonstrations have proven the role of this type accelerator technology for modern economy of any country .

1. Introduction

The physical, chemical, and biological effects of ionizing radiation on matter form the basis for many practical applications of accelerators [1]. The number of such applications is growing, and the sources based on electron accelerators, providing beam of electrons and X radiation (e/X conversion) are now being operated in diverse environments. Progress in the development of radiation technologies creates opportunities for their various industrial applications, especially in the field of materials engineering, medicine and agriculture or in environmental protection, which are covered by the Network WP 3 of ARIES. A diversified base of accelerators operated at INCT (Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and technology) [2] allows the implementation of new techniques of radiation technologies. The new challenges, including application of chemical and radiation techniques in the development of new pharmaceuticals, tissue and biomedical engineering, implants for reconstructive and surgical surgery, tissue banks and for the production of composite materials, nanomaterials, semiconductor products, issues related to nuclear energy and environmental protection were undertaken thanks to these possibilities. The polymer crosslinking is already applied on a big industrial scale [3]. There are the new fields of possible electron accelerators application, which can in the near future generate a growing demand for electron accelerators:

- Innovative high-performance carbon fiber composites;
- Self-healing polymer composites;
- Conducting Nano- and micro composites as sensors;
- Synthesis of nanomaterials;
- Radiation technologies in medically oriented applications;

- New crosslinkable polymers,
- Reduction in environmental pollution by the degradation of toxic compounds in air, water and soil.
- Cracking crude oil to increase the yield of lighter compounds that are the most valuable products.
- Increased sale of irradiated foods to reduce the use of toxic chemicals to control insects, and to reduce the risk of disease.
- Recovery of rare metals, such as scandium from effluents of hot spring by radiation grafted fiber absorbent (radiation grafted fibers for recovery of uranium from sea water)
- Radiation degradation of natural polymers, such as chitosan, starch and carrageenan to produce a plant growth promoter and super water absorbent for improving agriculture.

Further research on these technologies is needed. In this report, work related to the development of new processes like the polymer modification and microbial decontamination related to new technology development is reported. One may expect that advanced research related to science and technology of new acceleration concepts will initiate radiation technology applications in many new areas including energy, the environment, and infrastructure. The development of compact superconducting accelerators may open many new application areas in energy production such as petroleum upgrading, and liquefying gaseous products. The high power high-energy compact accelerator would be small enough to be installed as a mobile unit. This enables bringing the power of ionizing radiation to sites needing environmental remediation. New ideas of accelerators for radiation processing includes: superconducting RF compact, high power, electron linacs, eFFAG (**F**ixed-**F**ield **A**lternating **G**radient compact CW recirculating accelerators), compact CW linacs and number of other modern accelerator constructions.

2. New developments in accelerator engineering

2.1 THE REQUIREMENTS FOR CURRENT E-BEAM APPLICATIONS

Electron beam technology is now commonly accepted for research study and industrial implementation. A wide field of R&D study and business opportunities can be implemented in electron beam accelerator facilities. Various historical fields of applications include sterilization for single use medical items, cross-linking of insulation of wires and cables, modification of properties of polymers and semiconductors, and a number of other radiation technologies. The importance of radiation technology is related to its unique properties and the quality of irradiated products which can be obtained.

Before starting work for the installation of an electron beam facility, one should analyse the technical and economic parameters of the process. Specifically, the technical characteristics of the irradiation process with respect to product profile should be known, as well as the type of the facility proposed

based on the volume of the products to be irradiated. New accelerator ideas and construction technologies are being developed continuously to achieve efficient, inexpensive, reliable, high average beam power commercial units. Advances in high power switching technology, core amorphous ferromagnetic materials, modulator macro pulses technology, recirculation accelerators, CW operation of microwave generators, microwave generators based on direct switching of high power electron beams are being transferred to industrial accelerator development.

The most suitable type of accelerator for a certain application depends first on the required electron energy that is directly related to density and structure of irradiated objects, and on beam power that defines total capacity of the installation. The other technical and economical parameters that are usually taken into account are related to electrical efficiency of the accelerator, physical size, reliability, maintainability, and investment and operating costs. Computer based control systems are used commonly now, something that has simplified the operation of those complex devices.

The investment and operating costs for electron beam accelerators vary widely because of different accelerator specification, type of accelerator and accelerator producers. In general high facility throughput that is directly related to the beam current level may significantly reduce the total unit cost of the process. The accelerators with higher energy of electrons cost more than low energy devices with the same beam power level. Therefore, the lowest energy rating with suitable dose distribution in the irradiated object will give better economical parameters for the radiation process. Low energy transformer accelerators can provide high electron beam power with high efficiency for electrical energy conversion. They are limited in electron energy and sometime have a large physical size. High frequency resonant accelerators can be built for high electron energy level with relatively compact structure and quite high beam power. Their limitations are related to lower electrical efficiency, more complex construction of high frequency generators and higher exploitation costs (spare parts). The accelerator technology is based on a number of different accelerator constructions that can satisfy most of technical and economical requirements of radiation processing.

Major industrial accelerators producers are located in USA, Japan, Russia, France, Canada, China and Germany. Several other countries are capable to produce accelerators among them Poland but these instruments are often prototype constructions and used rather like pilot and R&D installations. Broader application of radiation technology may stimulate the national programs of accelerator development in future.

The progress in accelerator technology dedicated to industrial applications is closely related to the continuously advanced development in many branches of technology and to technology transition from research to commercially applicable systems. Accelerator application may play a major role in developing new big markets related to environmental applications of radiation processing. High power, high efficiency, low cost accelerator technology may need government support in design, construction and testing at a demonstration plant. Environmental applications of EB technology are examples of high risk and not very high payoff but radiation technology transfer to environmental application could result in a substantial improvement in public health. The continuous progress and new developments in accelerator technology has a great impact on progress in radiation processing

industry. It may also help to open a big market for electron beam technology applied for environment conservation.

The investment and operating costs for electron beam accelerators vary widely because of different accelerator specification, type of accelerator and accelerator producers. High facility throughput directly related to the beam current level may significantly reduce total unit cost of the process. The accelerators with higher energy of electrons cost more than low energy devices with the same beam power level. Therefore, the lowest energy rating with suitable dose distribution in irradiated object will give better economical parameters of the radiation process. A reduction of the operating time would increase the unit cost significantly because fixed annual cost of investment will be allocated to fewer hours of accelerator exploitation. On the other hand, the higher dose will increase the process throughput and reduce the unit costs.

Accelerator selection criteria are as follow:

- Average beam power (*productivity*),
- Electron energy (*penetration*),
- Price (*investment cost*),
- Electrical efficiency (*cost of accelerator exploitation*),
- Size (*building geometry and size*),
- Reliability (*availability >95%*).

Investment in general includes the cost of the accelerator and the necessary building with shielding walls, safety interlock system, conveyor and auxiliary equipment, land, documentation and installation. Investment cost is frequently connected to the bank credit and can become an important part of operation costs, in addition to labour and administration spending, electrical energy consumption and spare parts.

An economic and financial evaluation should be performed to obtain information about the commercial economic profitability of the project before its final approval and implementation. The economic evaluation should include the structure of investment and the operating cost of the radiation facility. The economic effects of radiation installation may be influenced by many factors. The most important are the following:

- Investment cost (direct and indirect costs);
- Operating cost (variable and fixed costs);
- Required dose level,
- Utilization of the electron beam and required dose homogeneity.

Cost reduction is one of the key factors in the successful implementation of radiation technology. Annual cash flow projections are common techniques used for analyses of economic options. Economic analysis based on annual fixed and variable costs evaluation is very useful to the prognosis and recognition of the accelerator facility economical condition. Estimated capital costs can be referred to electron accelerator price. One should take into account the expenses related to:

- Shielding walls,

- Ventilation,
- Building with armature,
- Technological equipment,
- Process control system,
- Design and permission,
- Installation and validation,

Capital costs (investment) K_k in relation to accelerator price (K_a) can vary in most cases according to the simple empirical formula given below:

$$K_k \sim 2.2 K_a$$

Capital costs (investment) includes direct and indirect cost component:

Direct costs

- The preparation of the stand;
- Construction of the building;
- Technological equipment;

Indirect costs

- Project management,
- Facility design,
- Installation,
- Commissioning,
- Reserve.

Service (exploitation) cost can be divided into fixed and variable. Investment cost may have primary influence on fixed service cost, due to assumption related to amortization rate (5-10 years).

Exploitation fixed costs:

- Administrative costs with overheads,
- Security, amortization, credit,
- Required license costs,
- Service (planned),
- Taxes including land tax,
- Insurance,
- Annual regulatory permit fees,
- Periodic verification or emission tests.

Exploitation variable costs:

- Labour (exploitation, supervision);
- Electricity, water, pressured air, others;
- Materials;
- Spare parts;

In general, electron beam technology seems to have low operating cost despite its moderate to high capital costs. The high capital cost of technology may be compensated for by its relatively low annual operating costs. A full set of technical information should be collected to describe accelerator quality and evaluate the risk connected with certain accelerator design.

The procedure of the realization of the investment should include certain steps:

1. Pre-feasibility study (multi variants conception),
2. The choice of the variant,
3. The study of feasibility - the chosen variant,
4. Project the conditions of the building and land development,
5. Obtaining the conditions of the buildings and land development,
6. Technical project of the building and project of permission on the building,
7. Obtaining permission on building,
8. The realization.

The initiation of investment process requires standard procedures related to acceptance (permission) of local authorities supported by a report related to potential influence on the environment. The specific procedures are related to permissions that are necessary to initiate construction, starting up and exploitation of facilities equipped with sources of ionizing radiation. Such permission are usually provided by Nuclear Safety Department of National Atomic Agency. Accelerator operators should obtain an official license to operate an accelerator facility. A formal proposal should be supplied to the Nuclear Safety Department of National Atomic Agency. After positive results of national examination the license will be provided. The training course on radiation safety matters for accelerator operators is strongly recommended in advance to national exam.

A detailed technical analysis should be performed to recognize the optimal conditions of the irradiation process depending on the geometry of the irradiated product, the nominal energy of the accelerator and the configuration of the irradiation process. Due to specific product dimensions, two-sided irradiation could be the solution to improve the process efficiency, and irradiation homogeneity. Such a process can be performed by an electron beam with energy 5 or 10 MeV. A more detailed financial analysis of the profitability of the process should be undertaken after selecting a certain accelerator to implement radiation processing. The possible reason of difference would be the specific beam utilization coefficient or significantly lower beam power provided by the facility. Other limits can be present due to the ability to perform the irradiation process fast enough (conveyor speed) to use full beam power. The detailed analysis should be performed regarding product profile and selection of irradiation configuration and conveyor technical capabilities and properties. Traditional conveyor systems seem to be more universal for different types of irradiated product.

2.2 THE POTENTIAL FOR NEW ACCELERATOR TECHNOLOGY TO BRING IMPROVEMENTS IN TERMS OF COST AND PERFORMANCE FOR ELECTRON BEAM APPLICATIONS

The total number of accelerators in operation in science, medicine and industry amounts currently to approximately 50.000 units. Industrial applications of accelerators covers many field of activities such as electron beam cutting and welding; non-destructive testing; ion implantation; ion beam analysis; radioisotope production; neutron generators; synchrotron radiation and electron beam radiation processing. Over 3.000 accelerators have been built for radiation processing since the mid-1950s, when the first accelerator was applied for large-scale radiation sterilization.

Progress in accelerators for radiation processing development can be divided into many stages:

- Adaptation of accelerators primarily built for scientific experiments;
- Electron energy and beam power increase in certain accelerator constructions;
- Accelerators for R&D, pilot plants and industrial facilities;
- Computer control systems for accelerator start up, full operation and technological process management;
- Reliability improvement according to industrial standards;
- Accelerator technology perfection (electrical efficiency, cost);
- Accelerators for MW power beam level;
- Compact and more efficient accelerator constructions;
- Very low energy, powerful accelerators.

Progress in accelerator technology development is based on new constructions and new components. Currently electron beams in the energy range 0.05–10 MeV and beam power up to 700 kW have a wide and growing spectrum of applications. There are three distinctly different kinds of activity in this field of development of radiation processing commercial applications:

- Development of radiation technology;
- Accelerator design and construction;
- Facility construction and technology optimization.

It should be noticed that many labs conduct R&D in accelerator physics but only a few private companies manufacture commercial electron accelerators and they are not ready to provide suitable resources for accelerator technology development. On the other hand new accelerator business can be successful only with new ideas in accelerator design and acceptable costs and performances.

Optimization of accelerator technology solutions towards commercial needs is necessary to promote industrial implementation of accelerators. The specific goals can be obtained to achieve success when applied:

- **Compact units** – smaller footprint means reduced building and infrastructure costs;
- **Cheaper** – reduced initial capital investment;
- **Higher beam power** – increased productivity, reduced unit cost;
- **Better electrical efficiency** – reduced operating costs;

- **More reliable** – reduced Mean Time Between Failure, easier maintenance;
- **Improved performance** – optimized towards application;
- **Easier to operate** – fits into the standard protocols and operations;
- **Repeatable** – confidentiality that the same outcome every time can be obtained.

2.2.1 Superconducting technology transfer from high energy physics accelerators

Recent developments in the field of superconducting technology is based on: construction of accelerating cavities coated by Nb₃Sn [4], with increased efficiency and reduced heat generation, new low heat leak RF power coupler designs, integrated electron gun construction which allows to limit the heat that leaks into the system, conduction cooling and cryocoolers systems, sufficient for the low heat generation, with no need for liquid cryogenes.

Table 1. Basic parameters comparison of accelerating sections for normal conducting and superconducting RF structures.

Normal conductivity RF structure	Superconducting RF structure
High accelerating gradient	High accelerating gradient
High frequency (1.3 – 5.7 GHz)	Mid-frequency (up to 1 GHz)
Low stored energy	Large stored energy
10 x larger dE/E	Very small dE/E
Low Q (quality factor $\approx 10^4$)	Large Q (quality factor $\approx 10^{11}$)
Reduced efficiency	High efficiency

A basic parameter comparison of normal conducting and superconducting RF structures is presented in Table 1. Superconducting innovative technologies may enable construction of a new class of compact, powerful and simple accelerators for radiation processing in the near future. They can be recognized as relatively inexpensive, efficient (> 80%), turn key operation, high reliability accelerator units with energy of 10 MeV and beam power up to 250 kW with rather small dimensions (size Ø 0.7m x 1.5 m long). Low cost magnetrons to provide RF power at costs up to 5 times less than present sources should be necessary for significantly reduced initial and exploitation costs of such units. Fig. 1 shows a simplified block diagram of a superconducting linac.

Fig. 1. Simplified block diagram of superconducting linac: 1 - electron gun, 2 - RF superconducting accelerating section, 3 - bending magnet, 4 - scanning magnet, 5 - output chamber, 6 - microwave power source, 7 - helium cryoplant

A superconducting radio frequency compact, high power, electron linac for transmutation was already manufactured by NIOWAVE Inc. (Fig. 2). Its basic parameters are as follow: electron energy 0.5 – 40 MeV, beam power 1 – 100 kW, average beam current up to 2,5 mA, frequency 350 MHz, electron bunch length ≈ 5 ps, electron gun voltage 100 kV.

Fig. 2. Superconducting radio frequency compact, high power, electron linac for transmutation manufactured by NIOWAVE Inc.

2.2.2 eFFAG (Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient) compact, CW, recirculating electron accelerator

The eFFAG (Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient) electron accelerator is characterized by compactness, CW operation and electron bunches recirculation. It is composed of separated permanent magnet components (Fig. 3). They provide a fixed magnetic field like a cyclotron. On the other hand, they follow synchrotron-like electron beam dynamics.

Fig. 3. eFFAG, CW, recirculating electron accelerator principle of operation

Currently permanent magnets based on ceramic ferrites (SmCo_5 or NdFeB) could be used. The other conceptual parameters can be as follow:

- High beam current: 1 – 2 mA,
- No power supplies for magnets,
- Inexpensive components,
- Compactness (<1 m diameter, transportable),
- A single 100-200 keV cavity (as in cyclotron),
- 45-90 acceleration turns,
- Duty cycle: 1ns/10 ns ~10%,
- Space charge limited to $\sim 10^9$ electrons/RF bunch,
- For 100 MHz cavity (10 ns bunch spacing),
- Injection voltage 50 keV,
- Electron Energy: 9 MeV,
- Average beam power: ~ 140 kW.

2.2.3 High power microtron

An interesting construction of a microtron accelerator was presented recently by Photon Production Lab. Co Ltd from Japan. This type of accelerator is usually characterized by high energy and relatively low beam power. The new design parameters are presented in Table 2. Such performance may be effectively used in radiation sterilization process. The significant advantages of the presented microtron design applied in radiation sterilization process are high energy (10 MeV), high average beam power (30 kW) and narrow spectrum (2 %). The other interesting feature of such an accelerator is its compactness, which can be seen on Fig. 4. Unfortunately the present price level is not very competitive with existing linacs, which are commonly used in radiation sterilization facilities.

Table 2. The basic parameters for microtron dedicated for radiation processing

Electron energy	8 – 10 MeV
Pulse current	0.3 A
Pulse width	5 μ s
Repetition rate	2000 Hz
Beam power	30 kW
Frequency	2856 MHz
Weight (main body)	800 kg
Body size	40 x 60 cm

Fig. 4. Overall view of accelerating structure of microtron

2.2.4 CW electron linear accelerator for industrial applications

CW linacs can provide high average power electron beams for high capacity industrial applications. Accelerators of this type are relatively simple and do not require a cryostat and some other devices which are necessary in superconducting linacs. In principle CW linacs are capable of generating electron beams with energy up to 10 MeV with hundred kilowatt average beam power. Unfortunately presently demonstrated designs can only offer 1 MeV electron beam with beam power 25 kW. The main development direction is connected with the design of compact easy-to-operate and easy to maintain electron accelerators with beam power of tens of kilowatts and energy range 1-2 MeV [5].

2.2.5 Permanent sealed compact e-beam accelerators

Low energy, permanently sealed, compact, ebeam accelerators were recently offered by Comet ebeam Technologies, Switzerland. They are hermetically sealed by brazing and welding. The accelerating section (Fig. 5.A) can be refurbished by milling out the frame with window foil and welding in new one when the window or cathode are broken. The guaranteed operating time amounts to 8000 hours. The voltage can be adjusted from 100 to 300 kV. Beam power up to 4.5 kW can be obtained. Beam intensity variation is typically within the range +/-5 %. The primary application could be surface curing for printing technology. The whole accelerator system is very compact, as shown in Fig. 5.B where accelerating section, high voltage generator, heat exchanger and control units are displayed.

A.

B.

Fig. 5. Low energy, permanently sealed, compact, ebeam accelerators offered by Comet ebeam Technologies, Switzerland. A - Accelerating section with linear cathode and sealed exit window, B – all components (accelerating section, high voltage generator, heat exchanger and control units)

2.2.6 Toroidal source of accelerated electrons

A novel electron beam source suitable for simplified irradiation of 3D-shaped surfaces like a seed disinfection process, polymer modification or volume irradiation of flue gas stream has been introduced by Fraunhofer Institute for Organic Electronics, Electron Beam and Plasma Technology FEP Dresden, Germany. Radially converging beams are formed in order to have an all side product treatment in single pass. The compact setting and reasonable price of the basic raw materials are additional advantage of the proposed accelerator structure.

The EB-Source for non-thermal processing consists of cold cathode electron source, which is stimulated by a low pressure DC plasma and an acceleration voltage > 100 kV. A fine-vacuum level is required only when a simple, cheap and long life plasma cathode is used without sensitive thin and hot wires. An initial glow discharge plasma follows naturally the cathode shape and an easily controllable beam current by plasma density is obtained.

Currently, operating parameters like a structure diameter free for irradiation 120 mm, accelerator voltage 120 kV, and beam power < 5 kW (current density $< 0,2$ mA/cm²) is obtained. Future modification is possible depending on the specific radiation process requirements. Fig. 6 shows the cross-section of the accelerating structure of the toroidal source of accelerated electrons.

Fig. 6. Toroidal accelerator principle of operation: HVPS – high voltage power supply, PG – plasma generator, 1 – metal cathode, 2 – grid, 3 – window support and output window foil, 4 – helium ion particles, 5 – secondary electrons, 6 – outside metal envelope.

Currently significant modifications of the toroidal accelerator concept are under consideration. Analysis of a 400 keV, beam power up to 150 kW and inner radius of 80-100 cm is being performed. Based on such analysis, a 4 MeV, 1 MW accelerator unit could be applied for a large scale wastewater system [6].

2.2.7 Second generation of accelerators Rhodotron® type

Significant efforts have been done to introduce into the market so call “Second generation Rhodotron® type accelerators” [7]. Pulsing of the RF system was implemented to achieve such goals like reduced power consumption, modular design of the RF power system, reduced size and implementing fast beam switching. A pseudo-simultaneous mode of operation with two window exits is an interesting approach which provides two beam lines (Fig. 7). It is characterized by different streams of ionizing radiation in the form of an e-beam and an X-ray stream which can be applied for radiation processing simultaneously with selected intensity and capacity of two separate product lines (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Time characteristic of pulsed beam for e-beam and X-ray configuration in “pseudo-simultaneous mode of operation”

Fig. 8. Schematic diagram of second generation Rhodotron® type accelerator able to irradiate simultaneously on two separate conveyor systems, using 10 MeV electron energy beam and 7 MeV X-ray stream obtained by fast switching

One of the main advantages of pseudo-simultaneous way of Rhodotron® operation in electron beam and X-ray modes is an increase in the total facility maximum throughput. The small capacity in X-ray can be compensated for by high throughput of high capacity e-beam operation.

2.2.8. Power sources for particle accelerator technology

High power pulsed modulators are based on component development. As an example, it can be mentioned that high voltage thyratrons were designed to stand peak forward anode voltage up to 100 kV with pulse current 10-100 kA and average current up to 50 A. A repetition rate up to 500 Hz can be obtained with a pulse duration of 1 μ s. Such instruments allow to build modulator systems that have both high peak power (>100 MW) and high average power (>1 MW).

Sharp progress in microwave generation technology provided new generation of instrument like gyrocons and magnicons. They are especially suitable for high power applications when their properties are significantly better compared with klystron technology. The microwave power up to 5 - 10 MW in the CW mode and pulse power 500 - 1000 MW can be obtained for certain device construction with an efficiency of 60-80%, at the wavelength range 2 cm - 1 m.

Microwave energy sources for electron acceleration should be characterized by low cost, compact construction, and high performances of the RF source. Klystrons, invented in late 1930s, commonly serve as a class A RF signal amplifier in many accelerators. Its amplification factor depends upon the number of RF cavities. They are available in wide range frequency, pulse and average RF power. Unfortunately its electrical efficiency is in the range of 40 %. Induction output tubes (IOTs) is a hybrid type device based on resonant circuit technology and grid modulation which became available in the early 1990s. Due to their compact nature, IOTs are considerably cheaper to purchase than the conventional klystron, and are suitable for particle accelerators [8]. IOTs are characterized by higher electrical efficiency but with typically lower power than klystrons. There is a significant need to improve current capabilities of RF sources, as demonstrated by magnetrons. They are practically installed into electron accelerator systems since the 1950s. This relatively simple and cheap self-excited device electrical efficiency is around 70 %. The improvements using new design technology are promising to obtain long lifetime magnetrons which will operate using solid state modulators with RF average power high enough for industrial accelerators used for environmental protection [9].

3. Testing of electron accelerator parameters requirements for their emerging technological applications

3.1 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON APPLICATION OF ACCELERATORS FOR EMERGING MATERIALS PROCESSING TECHNOLOGIES

3.1.1 Electron beam polymer grafting

Radiation-induced grafting is a useful tool for surface modification of a wide range of polymers dedicated to different applications. This method, thanks to the choice of suitable monomers (methacrylamides, acrylamides, methacrylates, acrylates, acrylonitrile, styrene, vinyl acetates, vinyl chlorides, acrylic acid, N-vinylpyrrolidone, N-isopropylacrylamide), enables the introduction of new properties to the polymer layer such as hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity, adhesion, barrier properties, friction resistance. Radiation grafting has found application in industry and medicine [10]. Currently, intensive work is being carried out in the field of polymer membranes (fuel cells membrane, battery separators), production of selective adsorbents (e.g. scandium, cesium, uranium adsorbents) or to design polymers for medical and biotechnological applications (thermosensitive cell culture surfaces, antibacterial masks, intelligent packagings). Among these applications, membrane systems are one of the most effective and fast-growing technologies used for separation and purification processes [10].

The grafting process initiated by gamma or electron beam (EB) radiation allows the easy control of the parameters of grafting (by the changes in the radiation exposure and reaction conditions, e.g. dose, dose rate, atmosphere, temperature), modify any type of synthetic and natural polymers in the various forms (film, fiber, membrane, fabric, powder), carry out the reaction in non-demanding conditions in a wide range of temperatures and obtain products with a high degree of purity, free from initiating agent or catalyst [11].

The modification of polymer surfaces can be achieved by conventional grafting (mutual and pre-irradiation technique) or by reversible addition-fragmentation chain transfer (RAFT)-mediated grafting methods as shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Pre-irradiation grafting using RAFT-mediated polymerization initiated by electron beam radiation.

In both cases, gamma rays or EB radiation can be used to generate active sites (free radicals) on polymeric surface which can then react with vinyl monomers to form a graft copolymer having a combination of properties of these compounds. Grafting by the RAFT-mediated method, in contrast to the conventional radiation grafting, enables the control of the length of the grafted chains (molecular weight, polydispersity), leading to new materials of different topologies and specific surface properties [12].

Research work in the field of radiation grafting at the Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology (INCT) has been carried out on the preparation of selective adsorbents of heavy ions [13, 14] and synthesis of polymers dedicated to medical applications for many years [15-17]. Both gamma radiation (^{60}Co) and electron beam radiation have been applied for these purposes. Experimental parameters (polymer nature, type and concentration of monomer, dose and dose rate, type of atmosphere, additives, etc.) affecting the grafting process were studied. Selection of irradiation facilities (gamma or electron beam irradiation) depends on the grafting system (type of polymer and reactivity of monomer) and the application of modified materials. In gamma sources, the dose rate is relatively low (kGy/h), while for electron beams it is high (kGy/s), therefore the irradiation time in a gamma source is much longer (hours) than when using a high energy electron beam (minutes or seconds). The higher the dose, the greater the amount of radicals is generated in the polymeric material, which has a direct impact on the degree of grafting. The dose rate affects the lifetime and concentration of radicals and the termination process as well. In mutual grafting, for the same dose, increase in the dose rate results in lower efficiency of grafting, because the high concentration of radicals increases yield of their recombination leading to a rapid termination process and to enhanced homopolymerization [18]. In general, grafting by the mutual method is usually performed using a gamma source, as compared to the pre-irradiation technique, where the preferred radiation is an electron beam [19]. The pre-irradiation method is useful when the access to accelerator or a gamma source is limited. Then, a polymer may be pre-irradiated (in air or in vacuum) and even after a certain storage time can be used to initiate the graft polymerization.

Experiments of radiation-induced grafting by pre-irradiation methods were performed at ambient temperature with a 10 MeV electron beam generated in a linear electron accelerator Elektronika 10/10 located in the Radiation Plant for Sterilization of Medical Devices. Grafting either by conventional or by RAFT-mediated polymerization was carried out in gamma sources with different dose rates at the Centre of Radiation Research and Technology at the INCT.

3.1.2 Electron beam surface microbial decontamination

The energy of the electrons is the parameter determining the ability of the beam to penetrate an irradiated object. Industrial electron beam accelerators can be divided into three major categories based on the energy of accelerated electrons:

- high-energy units (5.0 to 10 MeV);
- mid-energy (400 keV to 5.0 MeV);
- low-energy, self-shielded units (80 to 300 keV) [20].

In contrary to the high energy electron beam which can penetrate centimetres of irradiated material, the low energy electrons are absorbed over a few micrometers. There are number of factors which must be considered when determining the range of electrons having energy below 300 keV in an irradiated product. The penetration ability of low energy electron beam depends not only on the density of irradiated material but also on the accelerator's construction itself, like the thickness of the foil in the accelerator window and on irradiation conditions, because significant energy of the beam can be absorbed in air.

For the experiments on electron beam surface decontamination the ILU-6 accelerator at INCT was used. Accelerator ILU-6 - a resonant type machine which nominal operating range of the beam covers the energy range from 500 keV to 2 MeV. Lower electrons energy was achieved by reducing the accelerating field strength. The modification in pulse power supply system, arrangement of electron gun and beam sweep system of accelerator ILU-6 was performed. After accelerator modification energy of emitted electrons can be in the range 150 - 300 keV. Working parameters of modified ILU-6 accelerator are:

- Electrons energy range 150 – 300 keV
- Beam power up to 0.5 kW
- Average beam current up to 1 mA
- Puls duration $T_{imp} = 400 \mu s$ (const.)
- Pulse repetition rate 2, 3, 5, 10, 15, 25, 50 Hz
- Width of scanned beam up to 50 cm

For any irradiation process, the key parameter is the absorbed dose. In the case of a low energy electron beam, the control of the dose is problematic due to limited penetration of the beam in comparison to the thickness of most available dosimeters. For low energy electron radiation, a new

dosimetry term has been introduced, namely D_μ which is the dose in the first micrometre of an absorbing medium [21]. The other tested method for dose measurement when irradiating with a low energy electron beam is the application of specially constructed calorimeters [22].

The lower the thickness of a dosimeter the lower gradient of the dose that will be observed. One of the thinnest dosimeters available is RISO B3 dosimetric foil, which is manufactured as a highly-uniform, thin film with a nominal thickness $18\mu\text{m}$. Using a stack of B3 foil, it is possible to measure the range of electrons depending on the energy of the beam, as shown in the Fig.10. Examples of the beam range are presented for dosimetric foils irradiated using ILU 6 accelerator. The real energy of electron beam that the material was exposed to, was lower due to absorption in the $50\mu\text{m}$ Ti foil of the accelerator extraction window, and about 10 cm air gap between the window and the irradiated samples.

Fig.10. Range of electrons having energy 180, 230 and 300 keV measured in stack of B3 dosimetric foil irradiated using ILU 6 accelerator.

In the process where high energy electrons are used, the whole volume product is irradiated. However in recent years the application of low energy electron beam for surface microbial decontamination is being developed as an alternative to currently used highly penetrating ionizing radiation [23]. Since microorganisms reside mostly on the surface, the irradiation of the external layer should be sufficient to eliminate microorganisms. The effectiveness of such a beam in comparison with high energy electrons was proved for the reduction of microbial load in dried spices [24]. The low energy electrons can be used for surface microbial decontamination of seeds, flower bulbs or packaging. Elimination of the plant pathogens from the surface of flower bulbs can effectively inhibit the development of the plant disease, reduce spread of the pathogens and prevent the loss of the plants.

However, the effectiveness of surface microbial decontamination process using electron beam of energy below 300 keV depends on uniformity of the dose absorbed on the surface of irradiated products. Uniformity of absorbed dose distribution depends on the method of products delivering under the beam. In the INCT the solution were tested: for smaller samples (seeds or small onions) the rotating cylinder was used, as show in the Fig. 11.

Fig.11. Rotating cylinder used for samples irradiation with low energy electron beam.

The advantage of this solution is that:

- the dose of radiation was controlled by control of irradiation time. The longer time of irradiation of the sample - the higher reduction of the microbiological load.
- high dose uniformity on surface of irradiated products.

The disadvantage is that this solution can be only used in batch mode, which is not good from the practical point of view.

The other solution used was double side irradiation, like in case of tulip bulbs, show in Fig.12.

Fig.12. Tulip bulbs irradiated in the process of surface decontamination using electron beam.

There are advantages in application of low energy electron beam, which make it a promising technology for many applications. However, for its commercial application the most important is to develop method of products delivering under the beam that can be used for different size samples and in continuous operation mode. The factor that can affect the development of technology is the

availability of instruments like developed Comet Ebeam Technologies, Switzerland low energy, permanently sealed, compact, ebeam lamps, presented in Fig.5. In terms of energy conversion lower energy electron accelerators are more efficient. Thus this technology is more economically profitable and environmentally friendly. Accelerators generating beam of energy below 300 keV are constructed as self-shielded units, which makes them easy to be used in-line of existing processes.

3.1.3 Electron beam paper microbial decontamination

Paper provides the ideal nutrient base for mould fungi. Therefore, large volumes of books and archival collections are affected by bioburden because of improper storage conditions or accidents such as floods. Protection of books, archives and artifacts from destruction caused by insects and microorganisms is one of the main aims of the cultural heritage objects conservation. Moreover, the microbiological burden is harmful for the librarians' and archivists' health as well. Decontamination of microbiologically infected paper-based objects is a new area for the application of electron beam (EB) irradiation.

Currently the most common method used for decontamination of library and archival collections is ethylene oxide treatment, which is toxic to humans and the natural environment. Moreover, resistance of some microorganisms (e. g. *Pyronema domesticum*) to ethylene oxide has been observed [25]. The promising alternative for this technique can be ionizing radiation. Gamma irradiation has already been applied to the treatment of large volumes of books and archives as well as wooden sculptures [26-29]. However, the most prevalent literature on applications of ionizing radiation to paper-based objects decontamination was related to treatment with γ radiation, because of its high penetration. Nevertheless electron beam irradiation can be effectively applied for decontamination of biodeteriorated archives as well as for preventive conservation of large volumes of books in short time. Moreover, due to the high dose rate of EB irradiation, appropriate dose is delivered to the treated objects in several seconds therefore post-oxidation related effects of paper degradation are significantly limited.

The only one well-documented application of EB irradiation to decontamination of paper-based objects on large scale is the irradiation of mail to recipients at the Congress, the White House and federal agencies in the US that started in October 2001 after spores of the deadly bacterium anthrax were found in mail sent to members of the news media and congressional leaders.

According to available data, about 1.2 million containers of D.C. federal mail were irradiated from November 2001 through April 2008 [30]. Two different facilities were used to irradiate mail. A Rhodotron continuous wave electron beam accelerator (energy 10 MeV, power 170 kW) located in Bridgeport, New Jersey is applied for the mail irradiation with the dose of 56 kGy [31, 32]. Absorbed dose is measured with NIST (The National Institute of Standards and Technology) alanine reference dosimeters. A roller conveyor system is used to transfer boxes with the mail under electron beam. Mail must arrive packaged flat, double bagged, boxed, and sealed. Each box is irradiated twice, once

per side. Sealed boxes are manually flipped over for second pass. Dosimetry is performed on trays. The throughput is 2040 kg per hour.

The second facility is located in Lima, Ohio and is equipped with a single accelerator operating at energy 10 MeV and power 18 kW. A fixed-carrier conveyor system is being used to transfer boxes with the mail under the electron beam. The mail arrives packaged vertically in trays, double bagged, boxed, and sealed. Each box is irradiated four times (conveyor rotates boxes automatically for each pass). Dosimetry is performed on trays. Throughput is 450 kg per hour [32].

In the INCT, electron beam irradiation has been applied for the paper-based object sanitization for many years.

In the experiments on microbial decontamination of paper-based objects with electron beam application accelerator LAE 10/10 was used. Accelerator LAE 10/10 is microwave linear electron accelerator, with energy of 10 MeV, average beam power in the range of 10-15 kW. Operating parameters of LEA 10/10 accelerator used for microbial decontamination of paper are:

- electron energy 10 MeV
- average beam current 1 mA
- average beam power 10 kW
- pulse duration 2 - 6 μ s
- pulse repetition frequency 50 -300 Hz
- scanning frequency 1,2,5 Hz
- scanning length 65 cm
- microwave generator frequency 1886 MHz

The energy of electrons experiments was measured according to ISO/ASTM 51649:2015(E) “Standard Practice for Dosimetry in an Electron Beam Facility for Radiation Processing at Energies Between 300 keV and 25 MeV” using aluminum wedge and B3 dosimetric foil. The most probable electron beam energy measured was from 9.2 to 9.5 MeV.

Laboratory tests of different kinds of papers irradiated with wide ranges of doses (0.4-25 kGy) have been performed. Changes in mechanical, thermal, physicochemical and colour properties after paper irradiation were studied, together with the effectiveness of different absorbed radiation doses in *Aspergillus niger* elimination in different kinds of paper (fig. 21) [33]. Electron beam irradiation of samples was carried out using a 10 MeV, 10 kW linear electron accelerator Elektronika with dose rate 5×10^3 Gy/s. Delivered doses were confirmed using Gammachrome Harwell dosimeters for lower doses, and the calorimetric method involving graphite calorimeters was applied to measure absorbed radiation doses in a range from 5 to 25 kGy. Investigation of the optimisation of the irradiation procedure estimates a dose of 5 kGy as sufficient for the complete elimination of *A. niger* from all types of paper (even if the level of the contamination was very high $\sim 10^4$ - 10^5 CFU/cm²) and did not influence the studied optical, thermal, physicochemical and mechanical parameters of different papers.

Fig. 13. *A. niger* population on the different kinds of paper as a function of EB radiation absorbed dose.

Up to now ~ 200 m³ of archives, documents and books from different libraries, museums and collections were irradiated in the INCT.

Paper-based objects must arrive packaged flat (height of the box ~ 10 cm), boxed, and sealed. A roller conveyor system is used to transfer boxes under the electron beam. The speed of the conveyor system can be changed in order to ensure the delivery of the required dose. Each box is irradiated twice, once per side. Sealed boxes are manually flipped over for a second pass. The throughput is 2 m³/h. Dosimetry is performed on trays with the application of the calorimetric method involving graphite calorimeters.

The traceability of the required irradiation dose is ensured by the Laboratory for Measurements of Technological Doses (LMTD), which is a part of the INCT and is accredited by Polish Centre for Accreditation (PCA) as a testing laboratory according to the requirements of the PN-EN ISO/IEC 17025:2005 Standard.

4. Conclusions

The implementation of new technologies including radiation technologies, based on electron accelerator applications, is still a particularly difficult but promising task. Additional criteria should be added to the criteria set for basic research, the fulfilment of which will enable the chosen technology to achieve commercial success, namely the right time and place for implementation. These conditions are related to the demand for a given technology, which is determined not only by technical development, but also by expectations and social needs in a given country. They play an important role in the economic development of many countries. The work reported in Deliverable D3.2 covered a critical review of recent developments in accelerator engineering and experimental demonstration

of how these machines parameters have to meet requirements of emerging technologies to be implemented with their use.

New ideas of accelerators for radiation processing include: superconducting RF compact, high power, electron linacs, eFFAG (Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient compact CW recirculating accelerators), compact CW linacs and a number of other modern accelerator constructions. It should be noticed that many labs conduct R&D in accelerator physics but only a few private companies manufacture commercial electron accelerators and they are not ready to provide suitable resources for accelerator technology development. New business in the field of radiation processing can be successful only with new ideas in accelerator design with acceptable costs and performances.

The experimental part of the work covered demonstration of applicability of different accelerators to selected materials and processes. Two types of accelerator technologies were selected for such testing; those which require application of low energy beam (less than 300 keV) and highest applicable electron beam energy accepted for eb processing (10 MeV). Two accelerators have been used for testing. The first one was the single cavity, high frequency, pulsed accelerator ILU 6 (with adjustable electron energy up to 2 MeV) and the second the microwave linear electron accelerator, with travelling wave LAE 10/10. The construction principles of both units are different and some of accelerators being developed and described in the first part of the report are based on similar physics and electronic scientific background. Emerging radiation processing technologies selected for such demonstration needs for process and accelerator integration include electron beam polymers grafting, electron beam surface microbial decontamination, and electron beam paper microbial decontamination. Radiation - induced grafting is a useful tool for surface modification of a wide range of polymers dedicated to different applications. Depending of the product the technology requires application of low energy (ca.300 keV) electron beam (battery separators, foils etc) or high energy (10 MeV) beam (bulk materials – like adsorbents and other products treated in suspensions etc). The application of low energy electron beam (up to 300keV) for surface microbial decontamination is being developed as an alternative to currently used highly penetrating ionizing radiation (medical and food products, etc). The low energy electrons can be used for surface microbial decontamination of seeds, flower bulbs or packaging. Elimination of the plant pathogens from the surface of flower bulbs can effectively inhibit the development of the plant disease, reduce spread of the pathogens and prevent the loss of the plants. There are advantages in the application of low energy electron beam that make of it a promising technology for many applications. In terms of energy conversion lower energy electron accelerators are more efficient. The other emerging and very important application of electron accelerator applications is electron beam sanitation of library old books, manuscripts, archives and cultural heritage art crafts. In this case 10 MeV electron energy machines has been applied and both side irradiation is required if bulk items are treated (in some cases surface microbial decontamination maybe applied, but these are random cases).

This report covering information on the recent development of accelerator engineering and presenting the requirements for their parameters in practical applications is intended as a practical guide for accelerator developers and manufacturers. Experimental demonstration of the importance of these parameters matching with the process requirements gives valuable information for road map elaboration of further developments in accelerator engineering for these solutions that are being

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Deliverable: D3.2

Date: 07/11/2019

offered to the end users market. This report should be read together with D.3.1 “Application of electron beams in the environmental area”, which presented requirements regarding high power electron accelerators to be applied in environmental pollution technologies. These two reports covers a whole variety of accelerators applied in EB processing. .

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CFU	Colony-Forming Unit
CW	Continuous Wave
EB	Electron Beam
eFFAG	Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient electron accelerator
INCT	Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology, Warsaw, Poland
LMDIT	Laboratory for Measurements of Technological Doses
PCA	Polish Centre for Accreditation